

Preparation, Properties and Reactions of Some Cobalt(III) Complexes containing 2-Substituted Derivatives of 1,3-Diaminopropane.

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Complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{tnX})_3]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{tnX})]^{3+}$, where en = ethylenediamine and tnX = 1,3-diamino-2-propanol, 1,3-diamino-2-bromopropane or 1,3-diamino-2-chloropropane, are prepared and characterised. Their infrared and visible absorption spectra are measured. In the case of the 1,3-diamino-2-bromopropanebis-(ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) complex, the kinetics for base hydrolysis are investigated at 25° and the mechanism of the reaction briefly discussed.

PREVIOUS attempts to prepare the tris (1,3-diamino-2-propanol)-cobalt(III) complex (I) have been unsuccessful. In a recent effort to prepare this compound, Okamoto and Barefield¹ used several standard methods, but obtained only a dull purple bis (1,3-diamino-2-propoxo) cobalt(III) complex (II), in which the ligand in question acts as a tridentate.

1,3-diamino-2-propanol were incorrectly formulated.^{3,4} In spite of the smaller chelate ring strain which should exist in structure (I) compared with that in structure (II), as well as the known small coordinating power of alcohols towards cobalt(III), it is surprising that the tris(1,3-diamino-2-propanol) cobalt(III) complex has so far escaped direct synthesis. In this work, we now successfully obtained the bromide salt of this complex (I) as brown yellow crystals by an indirect method via base hydrolysis of the corresponding tris(1,3-diamino-2-bromopropane) cobalt(III) bromide, the latter being readily obtainable by the action of 1,3-diamino-2-bromopropane dihydrobromide on sodium tris(carbonato) cobalt(III) trihydrate. The complex (I) could also be crystallised as the nitrate salt, and the identity in the visible absorption spectra of the two salts implies that we are dealing with the same cation in the pure state. The infrared absorption spectra of these new complexes are very similar to that of a known sample of tris(1,3-diaminopropane) cobalt(III) chloride, except for a small number of additional absorption peaks. For tris(1,3-diamino-2-bromopropane) cobalt(III) bromide, an additional absorption peak appears at 675 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to C-Br stretch. For tris(1,3-diamino-2-propanol) cobalt(III) bromide, this peak at 675 cm^{-1} is absent, but two other peaks appear at 935 cm^{-1} and 3400 cm^{-1} , which are due to C-O and O-H stretch respectively. Thus infrared absorption data support the presence of a free OH group in the ligand of the complex. For tris(1,3-diamino-2-propanol) cobalt(III) nitrate, three additional peaks at 823 cm^{-1} , 935 cm^{-1} and 3400 cm^{-1} appear, the strong absorption at 823 cm^{-1} being characteristic of ionic nitrate.⁵ Inorganic nitrates are expected to show another characteristic absorption in the range 1350-1380 cm^{-1} , but in our present complex, this overlaps with, and so becomes indistinguishable from, a strong CH_2 vibration of the chelate ring.

For example, aeration of a solution of cobalt(II) chloride in the presence of 1,3-diamino-2-propanol and suspended charcoal, treatment of sodium tris(carbonato) cobalt(III) trihydrate with 1,3-diamino-2-propanol dihydrochloride, or heating chloropentamminecobalt(III) chloride with 1,3-diamino-2-propanol, all gave the same complex (II). An earlier report² on the preparation of (I) is in error, while in the classical cobalt(III) literature, complexes containing

By evaporating an aqueous solution of a mixture of 1,3-diaminopropane and *trans*-dichlorobis(ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride on a steam bath, Bailar and Work⁶ isolated 1,3-diaminopropanebis(ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride. A subsequent attempt to

apply this method to the preparation of the analogous 1, 3-diamino-2-propanol bis (ethylenediamine) cobalt (III) complex was unsuccessful, as the only isolable product was bis (1, 3-diamino 2-propoxo) bis (ethylenediamine)-*μ*-ethylenediaminedicobalt(III) chloride.⁷ We now succeeded in preparing the bromide salt of the desired complex indirectly via base hydrolysis of the corresponding 1,3-diamino-2-bromopropane bis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) bromide, the latter being readily obtainable by an extension of the method of Bailar & Work⁶ to anhydrous methanol as solvent. The chloride salt was similarly prepared from 1, 3-diamino-2-chloropropane bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) chloride. For this series of $[\text{Co en}_2 (\text{tnX})]^{3+}$ complexes, $\nu_{\text{C-Br}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ were observed at 675, 936, and 3400 cm^{-1} respectively, and except for these, the infrared absorption spectra were very similar to that of a known sample of 1, 3-diaminopropane bis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride. There is no band which may be unambiguously assigned to C-Cl stretch, due presumably to extensive mixing with other modes of vibration, particularly those of the NH_2 group. In any case, $\nu_{\text{C-Cl}}$ is expected to occur in regions where the CH_2 or the NH_2 rocking modes absorb significantly.

For both series of $[\text{Co} (\text{tnX})_2]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co en}_2 (\text{tnX})]^{3+}$ cations, each visible absorption spectrum is very similar both in extinction coefficient and in wavelength of maximum absorption to that of $[\text{Co en}_3]^{3+}$, thus providing further support to the suggestion that the tnX ligands are bidentate and coordinate to cobalt through nitrogen. A typical spectrum is shown in Figure 1. The brown-yellow colour is also indicative of the presence of hexaammine type of cobalt(III) complexes (c. f., aquapentammine and diaquatetraammine species are pink or purple).

Fig. 1. Visible absorption spectrum of the 1,3-diamino-2-propanol bis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) cation.

The present preparation of bidentate 1, 3-diamino-2-propanol complexes depends on the base hydrolysis of the corresponding 1, 3-diamino-2-bromopropane complexes.

Therefore it would be of interest to study the kinetics of the reaction and to discuss briefly its mechanism. To

avoid complications arising from competition between consecutive and simultaneous processes, tris (1, 3-diamino-2-bromopropane)-cobalt(III) bromide was not used for the kinetic experiments. Instead, the complex was supplied as the 1, 3-diamino-2-bromo-propane bis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) cation, and the reaction was studied in the presence of varying amounts of hydroxide ion at 25°, the ionic strength of the reaction mixture being kept at a constant value of 0.15 mol dm^{-3} by the addition of sodium nitrate. The increase in bromide concentrations was followed by a titrimetric method (Volhard) after the complex cations had been removed by a cation-exchange resin (Amberlite IR-120; H^+ form). In each experiment, the base was present in large excess so that its concentration remained virtually constant during the period at which the reaction was followed. Under such conditions, pseudo-first-order kinetics were observed, and the rate constants are collected in Table 1, where each entry represents the average of two constants determined from separate runs.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE BASE HYDROLYSIS OF THE 1,3-DIAMINO-2-BROMOPROPANE BIS (ETHYLENEDIAMINE) COBALT (III) CATION AT 25° AND IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.15 MOL DM^{-3} .

$[\text{NaOH}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s^{-1})
0.020	0.55
0.040	0.82
0.060	1.02
0.080	1.23
0.100	1.45

These results obey a two-term rate law of the form

$$k_{obs} = k_1 + k_2 [\text{OH}^-]$$

where $k_1 = 3.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 1.1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$. They may be discussed along lines similar to those well established in classical organic literature as demonstrated by the base hydrolysis of alkyl bromides⁸. Here the four groups, methyl, ethyl, *iso*-propyl, and *tert*-butyl, exemplify the main features of the reaction. For methyl and ethyl bromides, the mechanism of base hydrolysis is typically $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$, leading to a simple second-order rate-law while for *tert*-butyl bromide, the reaction is unimolecular with observed rates independent of hydroxide ion-concentration. The intermediate case of *iso*-propyl bromide is mechanistically marginal, and both $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ and $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ paths are observed simultaneously so that the resulting rate-law consists of both first-order and second-order terms. In general, higher normal alkyl groups behave basically like ethyl, higher secondary alkyl groups like *iso*-propyl, and higher tertiary alkyl groups like *tert*-butyl. Clearly, the base hydrolysis of the present 1, 3-diamino-2-bromopropane bis (ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) cation is expected to behave similarly to that of *iso*-propyl bromide, and a two-term rate-law is indeed observed. The ratio k_2/k_1

gives a measure of the relative importance of the two paths, and in this case its value is $31 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$, which is also comparable to that observed in the classical case of *iso*-propyl bromide ($20 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$).

Experimental

Preparations

Starting Materials: 1, 3-Diamino - 2 - propanol was supplied commercially (Merck) and used without further purification. From this compound, 1, 3-diamino-2-chloropropane dihydrochloride was prepared via the diphthalimide by the method of Appleton and Hall⁸. {Found: C, 19.7; H, 6.1; N, 15.4; Cl(total) 58.2%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_3\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_3$: C, 19.8; H, 6.1; N, 15.4; Cl (total) 58.6%} 1, 3-Diamino-2-bromopropane dihydrobromide was similarly obtained by the method of Mann⁹. {Found: C, 11.6; H, 3.6; N, 8.7; Br (total), 76.5%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_3\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{Br}_3$: C, 11.4; H, 3.5; N, 8.9; Br (total), 76.2%}.

Sodium tris (carbonato) cobaltate(III) trihydrate was prepared and purified by the method of Bauer and Drinkard², tris (1, 3-diaminopropane) cobalt(III) chloride and 1, 3-diaminopropanebis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride by the method of Bailar and Work⁶, and tris (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride by the method of Work¹⁰. *trans*-Dichlorobis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride was obtained from cobalt(II) chloride and ethylenediamine by the method of Bailar¹¹, except that hydrogen peroxide was used instead of atmospheric oxygen as the oxidising agent.

Tris (1, 3-diamino-2-bromopropane) cobalt(III) bromide: 1, 3-Diaminopropane dihydrobromide (4.5 g) and sodium tris carbonato-cobaltate(III) trihydrate (1.5 g) was dissolved in water (10 cm^3). The solution was evaporated on a steam bath until brown-yellow crystals appeared. These were filtered off, and recrystallised from hydrobromic acid (2 mol dm^{-3}) at 35°. The crystals obtained were dried at 100° in vacuo. Yield: 1.4 g. {Found: C, 14.8; H, 3.6; N, 10.9; Br (total), 62.8; Br (ionic) 31.7; Co, 7.4%. Calcd. for $[\text{Co}(\text{tnBr})_3]\text{Br}_3$: C, 14.2; H, 3.6; N, 11.1; Br (total), 63.2; Br (ionic) 31.6; Co, 7.8%}.

Tris (1,3-diamino-2-propanol) cobalt(III) bromide: Tris (1,3-diamino-2-bromopropane) cobalt(III) bromide (1 g) was dissolved in 2 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide solution (10 cm^3). Conc. hydrobromic acid was added until the pH of the solution was 3, and the mixture was poured into methanol (100 cm^3). Ether was then added with stirring and the brown-yellow solid was filtered off, and recrystallised by dissolving in the minimum amount of hydrobromic acid (2 mol dm^{-3}) followed by the addition of methanol. The crystals obtained were dried at 100° in vacuo. Yield: 0.6 g. {Found: C, 18.8; H, 5.1; N, 14.6; Br, 42.5; Co, 10.4%. Calcd. for $[\text{Co}(\text{tnOH})_3]\text{Br}_3$: C, 19.0; H, 5.3; N, 14.8; Br, 42.2; Co, 10.4%}.

Tris (1,3-diamino-2-propanol) cobalt(III) nitrate: A dilute aqueous solution of the bromide of the complex was passed through a column of anion-exchange resin (Amberlite IRA 400; NO_2^- form). The effluent and

washings were concentrated on a rotary evaporator, and conc. nitric acid was added dropwise until brown-yellow crystals just began to appear. After cooling the contents in ice, the crystals were filtered off, washed with methanol and dried at 100° in vacuo. Found: C, 19.6; H, 5.2; N, 23.6; Co, 11.7%. Calcd. for $[\text{Co}(\text{tnOH})_3](\text{NO}_3)_3$: C, 20.9; H, 5.8; N, 24.4; Co, 11.5%}.

1,3-Diamino-2-bromopropanebis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) bromide: A finely powdered mixture of *trans*-dichlorobis (ethylenediamine)-cobalt(III) chloride (1.2 g), 1,3-diamino-2-bromopropane dihydrobromide (1.4 g) and sodium methoxide (0.45 g) was refluxed in dried methanol (30 cm^3) in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a condenser and a dry-tube for half an hour, when the solution turned deep red. The methanol was distilled off and the residue washed with 10 cm^3 portions of methanol until the filtrate and washings were no longer red. The resulting solid was dissolved in a minimum amount of hydrobromic acid (2 mol dm^{-3}) at 35° and methanol was added dropwise until crystals just began to appear. After cooling the contents in ice, the crystals, which consisted of essentially tris (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) bromide were filtered off and discarded. Ether was then added to the filtrate until brown-yellow crystals just began to appear. The contents were cooled in ice, and the crystals were filtered off, recrystallised and dried at 100° in vacuo. Yield: 0.6 g. {Found: C, 14.5; H, 4.2; N, 14.6; Br (total), 56.2; Br (ionic), 41.9; Co, 10.7%. Calcd. for $[\text{Co en}_3(\text{tnBr})]\text{Br}_3$: C, 14.7; H, 4.4; N, 14.7; Br (total), 56.0; Br (ionic), 42.0; Co, 10. %}.

1,3-Diamino-2 chloropropanebis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride: This complex was prepared and purified by a method similar to that described for 1,3-diamino-2-bromopropanebis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) bromide except that 1,3-diamino-2-chloropropane dihydrochloride (0.8 g) and hydrochloric acid respectively were used instead. Yield: 0.4 g. {Found: C, 21.2; H, 5.6; N, 20.9; Cl (total), 36.1; Cl (ionic), 27.0; Co, 15.4%. Calcd. for $[\text{Co en}_2(\text{tnCl})]\text{Cl}_2$: C, 21.3; H, 6.3; N, 21.3; Cl (total), 36.0; Cl (ionic), 27.0; Co, 15.0%}.

1,3-Diamino-2-propanolbis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) salts: The bromide salt was prepared from 1,3-diamino-2-bromopropanebis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) bromide (1 g) by a method similar to that used for tris (1,3-diamino-2-propanol) cobalt(III) bromide. Yield: 0.7 g. {Found: C, 18.2; H, 4.8; N, 16.3; Br, 46.0; Co, 12.0%. Calcd. for $[\text{Co en}_2(\text{tnOH})]\text{Br}_2$: C, 16.5; H, 5.1; N, 16.5; Br, 47.1; Co, 11.6%}. The chloride salt was similarly prepared from 1,3-diamino-2-chloropropanebis (ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride. {Found: C, 22.1; H, 6.4; N, 21.8; Cl, 28.6; Co, 15.0%. Calcd. for $[\text{Co en}_2(\text{tnOH})]\text{Cl}_2$: C, 22.4; H, 6.9; N, 22.4; Cl, 28.4; Co, 15.7%}. The nitrate salt was prepared from the bromide salt by a method similar to that used for tris (1,3-diamino-2-propanol) cobalt(III) nitrate. {Found: C, 18.5; H, 5.6; N, 27.9; Co, 12.9%. Calcd. for $[\text{Co en}_2(\text{tnOH})](\text{NO}_3)_2$: C, 18.5; H, 5.7; N, 27.7; Co, 13.0%}.

Kinetics :

Appropriate amounts of the complex and aqueous sodium hydroxide solution of the desired concentration and ionic strength were brought to reaction temperature in separate flasks. The alkali solution was then poured on the complex, which dissolved immediately. This time was taken as zero, and aliquot samples were withdrawn from time to time and delivered into vessels containing an excess of nitric acid. The "killed" solutions were then passed down a column containing Amberlite IR-120 resin (H^+ form), and the effluent and washings were analysed quantitatively for bromide ion by the Volhard method.

The thermostat used was of the conventional design capable of holding temperatures constant to $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The de-ionised water used for kinetic studies was freed from dissolved carbon dioxide by boiling and then cooling under an atmosphere of nitrogen. Light was carefully excluded from the reaction solution as a routine precaution.

Measurements :

Elemental microanalyses were by either the Australian Microanalytical Service, Melbourne or Alfred Bernhardt Mikroanalytisches Laboratorium, West Germany. Ionic naldides were estimated by passing a freshly prepared solution containing a known weight of the complex through a cation exchange resin column (Amberlite IR-120 ; H^+ form) and analysing the effluent and washings by the Volhard method. Infrared absorption spectra were measured with a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrometer on the solid complexes which were milled with Nujol and placed between KBr plates. Visible

absorption spectra were measured with a Unicam SP 800 spectrophotometer using silica cells.

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